

Live Social Distance Detection Using Deep Learning Model

Dr. E.K. Vellingiriraj ME., Ph.D.,¹, G.Sanmuga Priya²

¹Head of Department in MCA Department, Nandha Engineering College
(Autonomous), Erode, Tamilnadu, India.

²Final MCA, Department of Computer Applications, Nandha Engineering
College, (Autonomous), Erode, Tamilnadu, India.

Email: ¹giri@nandhaengg.com, ²priyaganesh5499@gmail.com

Abstract: To prevent the spreading of COVID, the only way is social distancing. Nowadays, AI teams create social distancing tools using the computer vision concepts. This project proposed a methodology to find social distance with the help of deep learning to evaluation the distance between people for mitigating the impact of corona virus pandemic. The detection tool was developed to notify people to keep safe safety distance among each other through evaluation of a video input feed. The video frame from 'mp4' file was given as input, and object detection pre-trained model based on YOLOv3 algorithm was applied for pedestrian detection. Then, video frame was converted into top-down view to measure distance from 2D plane. The distance among people was estimated and any noncompliant pair of people in display is indicated with red frame and red line. The proposed method was validated on pre-recorded video for pedestrians walking on street. The output result verified that proposed method is able to determine social distancing measures between people group in the video. The developed technique may be further developed as detection tool in real time application. The project is designed using Python 3.5 with opencv python 4.2.

Keywords— Social Distance Monitoring, Covid 19, Human Object Detection.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Social Distancing Sensor, the weights of the YOLO v3 Object Discovery Algorithm and the COCO dataset are used which are fluently available online. Also, the main library being used will be the OpenCV along with the Deep Neural Network (DNN) module.

When the new coronavirus (Covid-19) epidemic emerges, the spread of the contagion has left public upkeep anxiety if they don't have any effective cure. The World Health Organization (WHO) has declared Covid-19 as a epidemic due to the increase in the number of cases reported around

the world. To contain the epidemic, numerous countries have enforced a lockdown where the government executed that the citizens to stay at home during this critical period. The public health bodies similar as the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) had to make it clear that the most effective way to decelerate down the spread of Covid-19 is by avoiding close contact with other people.

To flatten the wind on the Covid-19 epidemic, the citizens around the world are rehearsing physical distancing. To apply social distancing, group conditioning and congregations similar as trip, meetings, gatherings, shops, soliciting had been banned during the counterblockade period. The people are encouraged to use phone and dispatch to manage and conduct events as much as possible to minimize the person-to-person contact.

To further contain the spread of the contagion, people are also informed to perform hygiene measures similar as constantly washing hands, wearing mask and avoiding close contact with people who are ill. Still, there's a difference between knowing what to do to reduce the transmission of the contagion and putting them into practice. The world has not yet completely recover from this epidemic and the vaccine that can effectively treat Covid-19 is yet to be discovered. Still, to reduce the impact of the epidemic on the country's frugality, several governments have allowed a limited number of profitable conditioning to be proceeded once the number of new cases of Covid-10 has dropped below a certain position.

As these countries cautiously resuming their profitable conditioning, enterprises have surfaced regarding plant safety in the newpost-Covid-19 terrain. To reduce the possibility of infection, it's advised that people should avoid any person-to-person contact similar as shaking hands and they should maintain a distance of at least 1 cadence from each other. In Malaysia, the Ministry of Health Malaysia (MOHM) has recommended several complaint forestallment measures for workplaces, individualities, and families at

home, seminars, childcare centres, and elderly living installations.

These measures include enforcing social distancing measures, adding physical space between workers at the plant, stunning work schedules, dwindling social connections in the plant, limiting large work-related gatherings, limiting unnecessary work trip, performing regular health checks of staff and callers entering structures, reducing physical conditioning especially for associations that have staff in the high-threat order, and conducting company events or conditioning online. Individualities, communities, businesses, and healthcare associations are all part of a community with their responsibility to alleviate the spread of the Covid-19 complaint.

In reducing the impact of this coronavirus epidemic, rehearsing social distancing and tone-insulation have been supposed as the most effective ways to break the chain of infections after resuming the profitable conditioning. In fact, it has been observed that there are numerous people who are ignoring public health measures, especially with respect to social distancing. It's accessible that given the people's excitement to start working again, they occasionally tend to forget or neglect the perpetration of social distancing.

Hence, this work aims to grease the enforcement of social distancing by furnishing automated discovery of social distance violation in workplaces and public areas using a deep literacy model. In the area of machine literacy and computer vision, there are different styles that can be used for object discovery. These styles can also be applied to descry the social distance between people.

II. RELATED WORKS

[1] IMPLEMENTATION OF MITIGATION STRATEGIES FOR COMMUNITIES WITH LOCAL COVID-19

In this paper, WHO is issuing the COVID-19 Strategic Preparedness and Response Plan (SPRP) for 2021 and accompanying documents as a package aimed at guiding the coordinated action that we must take at public, indigenous, and global situations to overcome the ongoing challenges in the response to COVID-19, address injuries, and compass a course out of the epidemic. Over the once time, much has been achieved by public authorities and communities with the support of WHO, benefactors and mates, and an unknown trouble by the scientific community and the private sector.

The Strategic Preparedness and Response Plan 2021 (SPRP2021) builds on what we've learned about the contagion and our collaborative response over the course of 2020, and translates that knowledge into strategic conduct. This plan builds on achievements and also focuses on the new challenges, to alleviate, for illustration, pitfalls related to new variants. The plan also considers the road we required to travel the safe, indifferent and efficient delivery

of diagnostics as well as vaccines as part of overall strategies to successfully attack the COVID-19 epidemic.

The coronavirus epidemic has affected millions of people across the world and has redounded in numerous lives being lost. To cover people from COVID-19, vaccines are being developed. Vaccination is a critical intervention to cover populations from COVID-19, especially in combination with crucial behavioural conduct.

The epidemic has exposed the world to several issues related to vaccine uptake. One crucial issue is dealing with adult vaccination and limited experience in managing it. In addition, vaccine hesitancy has increased steadily in over 90 of countries since 2014. The entire countries globally must take steps to understand the extent as well as nature of the hesitancy and then to start promoting the approved COVID-19 vaccines.

Too Important clashing information on vaccines, misinformation and intimation have the eventuality to impact people's stations, beliefs, knowledge and intention to accept vaccination. Digital platforms can be means for circulating rumours, which might also travel beyond the digital space ; in traditional media / in communities, from one person to other. Feedbacks from communities constantly show that due to influence of misinformation, intimation and rumours, numerous community groups across the globe believe a cure either formerly exists or they calculate on herbal remedies and other unproven treatments. The differences among vaccines, cures and treatments are still unclear for numerous people.

As leader of the global incident operation support platoon (IMST) structure, the UN Crisis Management Team (UNCMT), and as a author of the Access to COVID-19 Tools (ACT) Accelerator, WHO harnesses the world's specialized and functional moxie to restate knowledge into coordinated action.

[2] IMPLEMENTATION OF MITIGATION STRATEGIES FOR COMMUNITIES WITH LOCAL COVID-19 TRANSMISSION

This document describes the pretensions, guiding principles, and strategies for community mitigation to reduce or help original COVID-19 transmission. Community mitigation conditioning are conduct that people and communities can take to decelerate the spread of a new contagion with epidemic eventuality. COVID-19 is an contagious complaint caused by a new coronavirus. Community mitigation conduct are especially important before a vaccine or remedial medicine becomes extensively available.

Because COVID-19 is largely transmittable and can be spread by people who don't know they've the complaint, threat of transmission within a community can be delicate to determine. Until broad-scale testing is extensively enforced or we've a further comprehensive and precise measure of complaint burden, countries and communities should assume some community transmission or spread is being.

Individualities need to follow healthy hygiene practices, stay at home when sick, practice physical distancing to lower the threat of complaint spread, and use a cloth face covering (with some exceptions) in community settings when physical distancing can not be maintained. These universal preventives are applicable anyhow of the extent of mitigation demanded.

Guarding the public's health is consummate. As communities work to reduce the spread of COVID-19, they're also addressing the profitable, social, and secondary health consequences of the complaint. State, original, ethnical, and territorial officers are best deposited to determine the position of mitigation needed. Mitigation strategies should be doable, practical, and respectable; they should be acclimatized to the requirements of each community and enforced in a manner that minimizes both morbidity and mortality from COVID-19 and doesn't produce or complicate any health difference.

The information that follows provides a frame for countries and points as they consider which conduct to take to alleviate community transmission of COVID-19 in the United States. Selection and perpetration of these conduct should be guided by the extent of complaint transmission (Table 1). Demographic and other community characteristics, as well public health and healthcare system capacity, will also drive decision making on mitigation (Table 2). Eventually, a set of possible cross-cutting mitigation strategies for communities to consider is outlined.

[3] IMAGENET CLASSIFICATION WITH DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

In this paper [3] the authors use deep convolutional neural network for classifying 1.1 million high-resolution images in ImageNet LSVRC-2010 contest to 900 different classes. Here in this test data, they tried to achieve a) top-1 and b) top-5 error rates with 37.5 and 17.0, independently, which are better than the previous state-of-the-art methods. The given neural network, which has 50 million parameters with neurons, consists of 5 convolutional layers, some of them are also followed by maximum-pooling layers, also three completely connected layers with final 1000-way of softmax.

To make training briskly, we used non-saturating neurons and a veritably effective GPU perpetration of the complication operation. To reduce overfitting in the completely connected layers they employed a lately developed regularization system called "powerhouse" that proved to be veritably effective. They also gave a variant of this proposed model in the ILSVRC-2012 competition and tried to achieve a top-5 test error rate of 15.2, compared to 26.1 achieved by alternate entry.

Four times ago, a paper by Yann LeCun and his collaborators was rejected by the leading computer vision conference on the grounds that it used neural networks and thus provided no sapience into how to design a vision system. At the time, utmost computer vision experimenters

believed that a vision system demanded to be precisely hand-designed using a detailed understanding of the nature of the task. They assumed that the task of classifying objects in natural images would noway be answered by simply presenting exemplifications of images and the names of the objects they contained to a neural network that acquired the entire knowledge grounded on this training data.

What numerous in the vision exploration community failed to appreciate was that styles that bear careful hand-engineering by a programmer who understands the sphere don't gauge as well as styles that replace the programmer with a important general-purpose literacy procedure. With enough calculation and enough data, learning beats programming for complicated tasks that bear the integration of numerous different, noisy cues. Four times ago, while they were at the University of Toronto, our deep neural network called SuperVision nearly halved the error rate for feting objects in natural images and started an overdue paradigm shift in computer vision. Figure 4 shows some exemplifications of what SuperVision can do.

[4] VERY DEEP CONVOLUTIONAL NETWORKS FOR LARGE-SCALE IMAGE RECOGNITION

In this paper [4] the authors delved the effect of convolutional network depth on its delicacy in large-scale image recognition setting. Their main donation is a thorough evaluation of the networks of adding depth using an armature with veritably small (3x3) complication pollutants, that shows a significant enhancement on previous-art configurations that could be achieved by pushing depth to 16-19 weight layers.

These findings were base of their ImageNet Challenge 2014 submission, where their platoon secured first and the alternate places in the localization and bracket tracks independently. They also showed that their representations generalise well to other datasets, where they achieved state-of-the-art results. They have made their two best-performing ConvNet models intimately available to grease farther exploration on use of the deep visual representations in computer vision.

During training, input to their ConvNets is a fixed-size 224x224 RGB image. The only pre-processing they did is abating the mean RGB value, reckoned on training set, from each pixel. The image is passed through mound of convolutional (conv.) layers, where they used pollutants with veritably small open field 3x3 (which is lowest size for capturing the notion of leftism/ right, up/ down, center). In one of the configurations, they also employed 1x1 convolution pollutants, which can be seen as the direct metamorphosis of the input channels (followed by non-linearity).

III. METHODOLOGY

IMAGE SELECTION

Then image is named from the operation brochure itself. Any color image can be taken as input.

SETUP FOR NEURAL NETWORK

Then setup lines are set to load the yolov3 config and weights data along with coco names data set data so that mortal object presence discovery in the given image frame. This data is loaded for training purposes so as to fete the mortal object in the frames recaptured from the videotape. This data preserves as a training objects.

IMAGE EXTRACTION FROM Videotape

Then, the videotape train is taken from vids brochure and using cv2 module, the frames are resolve from the traintaken. However, it's resized into 480 pixels, If the train confines are above 480. In machine literacy, pattern recognition, and image processing, point birth starts from an original set of measured data and builds deduced values (features) intended to be instructional andnon-redundant, easing the posterior literacy and conception way, and in some cases leading to better mortal interpretations. Point birth is related to dimensionality reduction.

Mortal OBJECT Discovery On WITH DISTANCE BETWEEN TWO OBJECTS

Then, image processing is carried out similar that " person" classifier score is calculated and also if the confidence value is above0.5 also, it's honored as mortal and a bounding box is drawn for each mortal object inside the frame.

Also, euclidian distance between center points of two bounding boxes are calculated and if it plant to be lower than imbrication threshold, also red boxes are drawn above the green bounding boxes so that those two mortal are violating covid social distance. Every object class has its own special features that helps in classifying the class – for illustration all circles are round. Object class discovery uses these special features. For illustration, when looking for circles, objects that are at a particular distance from a point (i.e. the center) are sought. Also, when looking for places, objects that are vertical at corners and have equal side lengths are demanded. A analogous approach is used for face identification where eyes, nose, and lips can be plant and features like skin color and distance between eyes can be plant.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This project solved the problem of social distance measure in the given image frames between two human objects to alert/avoid the covid problem.

This design introduces the methodology of social distancing discovery tool using a deep literacy model. By using computer vision, the distance between people is estimated and any noncompliant brace of people is indicated with a red frame and a red line. The proposed system is validated using a videotape showing climbers walking on a road. In being system, image accession is carried out by first opting the videotape train and resolve them into frames. Also the images are taken for rambler discovery. For better results, images can be resizedhere. However, will be indicated with red lines that serve as preventative warnings, If the distance lower than the respectable distance between any two individualities.

The YOLO trained on the COCO dataset which consists of 80 markers like 'person', etc including mortal or rambler class. In this work, the only box equals, object confidence and pedestrian object class from discovery result in the YOLO model were used for rambler discovery. Confidence value for marker "person" is acclimated then with dereliction value set as 0.5.

The visualization results showed that the new system is able to determine the social distancing measures between people which can be further developed for use in other terrain similar as office, eatery, and academy. In addition, the work can be further bettered by optimizing the rambler discovery algorithm, integrating other discovery algorithms similar as mask discovery and mortal body temperature discovery, if the computing power of the tackle is bettered, and calibrating the camera perspective view.

V. CONCLUSION

This design answered the problem of social distance measure in the given image frames between two mortal objects to warn/ avoid the covid problem. This design introduces the methodology of social distancing discovery tool using a deep literacy model. By using computer vision, the distance between people is estimated and any noncompliant brace of people is indicated with a red frame and a red line. The proposed system is validated using a videotape showing climbers walking on a road. The visualization results showed that the new system is able to determine the social distancing measures between people which can be further developed for use in other terrain similar as office, eatery, and academy. In addition, the work can be further bettered by optimizing the rambler discovery algorithm, integrating other discovery algorithms similar as mask discovery and mortal body temperature discovery, if the computing power of the tackle is bettered, and calibrating the camera perspective view. The system is veritably flexible and stoner-friendly, so the conservation grounded on the changing terrain and conditions can be incorporated fluently. Any changes that are likely to beget failures are averted with security and preventative measures could be taken. The coding is done in accessible and flexible system program which helps easy changing. Since Python is veritably flexible programming language, stoner can fluently incorporate any modular program in the operation.

VI. REFRENCES

[1] Centers for Disease Control (CDC). Implementation of Mitigation Strategies for Communities with Local COVID-

19 [Online]. Available at: <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019> (Accessed 8 May 2020).

[2] Centers for Disease Control (CDC). Implementation of Mitigation Strategies for Communities with Local COVID-19 Transmission [Online]. Available at <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/downloads/community-mitigation-strategy.pdf> (Accessed 8 May 2020).

[3] Ministry of Health Malaysia (MOHM) Official Portal. COVID-19 (Guidelines) [Online]. Available at <https://www.moh.gov.my/index.php/pages/view/2019-ncov-wuhanguidelines> (Accessed 8 May 2020).

[4] D.T. Nguyen, W. Li, P.O. Ogunbona, "Human detection from images and videos: A survey", *Pattern Recognition*, 51:148-75, 2016.

[5] A. Krizhevsky, I. Sutskever, G.E. Hinton, "Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks", In *Advances in neural information processing systems*, pp. 1097-1105, 2012.

[6] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher, L.-J. Li, K. Li, L. Fei-Fei, "ImageNet: A Large-Scale Hierarchical Image Database", In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 2009.

[11] C. Fellbaum. *WordNet: An Electronic Lexical Database*. Bradford Books, 1998.

[12] L. von Ahn and L. Dabbish. Labeling images with a computer game. In *CHI04*, pages 319–326, 2004.

[13] R. Fergus, L. Fei-Fei, P. Perona, and A. Zisserman. Learning object categories from google's image search. In *ICCV05*, pages II: 1816– 1823, 2005.

[14] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman. Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1556*, 2014.

[15] C. Szegedy, W. Liu, Y. Jia, P. Sermanet, S. Reed, D. Anguelov, D. Erhan, V. Vanhoucke, and A. Rabinovich. Going deeper with convolutions. In *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 1–9, 2015.

[16] D. Erhan, C. Szegedy, A. Toshev, and D. Anguelov. Scalable object detection using deep neural networks. In *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), 2014 IEEE Conference on*, pages 2155–2162. IEEE, 2014.

[17] F. Schroff, D. Kalenichenko, and J. Philbin. Facenet: A uni-fied embedding for face recognition and clustering. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1503.03832*, 2015.